

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 97

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 97

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 97:1 "The LORD ¹reigns, let the ^bearth rejoice; Let the many ²islands be glad. ² "Clouds and thick darkness surround Him; ^bRighteousness and justice are the foundation of His throne. ³ "Fire goes before Him And ^bburns up His adversaries round about. ⁴ His "lightnings lit up the world; The earth saw and ^btrembled. ⁵ The mountains "melted like wax at the presence of the LORD, At the presence of the ^bLord of the whole earth. ⁶ The "heavens declare His righteousness, And ^ball the peoples have seen His glory.</p> <p>Psa. 97:7 Let all those be ashamed who serve "graven images, Who boast themselves of ^bidols; ¹Worship Him, all you ²gods. ⁸ Zion ¹heard <i>this</i> and "was glad, And the daughters of Judah have rejoiced Because of Your judgments, O LORD. ⁹ For You are the LORD "Most High over all the earth; You are exalted far ^babove all ¹gods.</p>	<p>Psa. 97:1 יְהוָה מֶלֶךְ תִּגְלֵל הָאָרֶץ וְשָׂמְחוּ אֲרָצִים רַבִּים : ² עֲנָנִים וְעָרָפֶל סָבִיבוֹ צִדְקָה וְיִמְשֻׁפֵּט מִכּוֹן כְּסֹאוֹ : ³ אֵשׁ לְפָנָיו תִּלְדָּה וּתְלַהֵט סָבִיב צָרָיו : ⁴ הַתַּיִרוֹ בְּרָקָיו תִּבְלֵ רְאֵתָהּ וּתְחַל הָאָרֶץ : ⁵ הָרִים כַּדֹּזָנִים נִמְסוּ מִלְּפָנֵי יְהוָה מִלְּפָנֵי אַדְוָן כָּל־ הָאָרֶץ : ⁶ הַתַּיִדֹת הַשָּׁמַיִם צִדְקוֹ וְרָאוּ כָל־הָעַמִּים כְּבוֹדוֹ : ⁷ יִבְשׂוּ כָל־עֵבְרֵי פֶסֶל הַמִּתְהַלְלִים בַּאֲלֵהִים הַשֹּׁתֵתוֹ לֹא כָל־ אֱלֹהִים : ⁸ שָׁמְעָה וַתִּשְׂמַח אֲצִיּוֹן וַתִּגְלֶנֶה בָּנוֹת יְהוּדָה לְמַעַן מִשְׁפִּיךְ יְהוָה : ⁹ כִּי־אַתָּה יְהוָה עֲלִיּוֹן עַל־כָּל־הָאָרֶץ מֵאֵד נֶעְלִית עַל־כָּל־אֱלֹהִים : ¹⁰ אִהְבֵּי יְהוָה שְׂנֵאוֹ רַע שָׁמַר נִפְשׁוֹת חֹסִידָיו מִיַּד רְשָׁעִים יִצְיָלֵם : ¹¹ אֹרֶז זָרַע לְצַדִּיק וְלִישְׂרָיִלֵב שָׁמְחָה : ¹² שָׁמְחוּ צַדִּיקִים בְּיְהוָה יְהוֹדוּ לְזִכְרֵךְ קִדְשׁוֹ :</p>

Psa. 97:10 ^aHate evil, you who love the LORD,

Who ^bpreserves the souls of His godly ones;

He ^cdelivers them from the hand of the wicked.

¹¹ ^aLight is sown *like seed* for the righteous

And ^bgladness for the upright in heart.

¹² Be ^aglad in the LORD, you righteous ones,

And ^bgive thanks ¹to His holy name.

References

Psalm 97:1

¹Or *has assumed Kingship*

²Or *coastlands*

^aPs 96:10

^bPs 96:11

^cIs 42:10, 12

Psalm 97:2

^aEx 19:9; Deut 4:11; 1 Kin 8:12; Ps 18:11

^bPs 89:14

Psalm 97:3

^aPs 18:8; 50:3; Dan 7:10; Hab 3:5

^bMal 4:1; Heb 12:29

Psalm 97:4

^aEx 19:16; Ps 77:18

^bPs 96:9; 104:32

Psalm 97:5

^aPs 46:6; Amos 9:5; Mic 1:4; Nah 1:5

^bJosh 3:11

Psalm 97:6

^aPs 19:1; 50:6

^bPs 98:2; Is 6:3; 40:5; 66:18

Psalm 97:7

¹Or *All the gods have worshiped Him*

²Or *supernatural powers*

^aPs 78:58; Is 42:17; 44:9, 11; Jer 10:14

^bPs 106:36; Jer 50:2; Hab 2:18

^cHeb 1:6

Psalm 97:8

¹Or possibly *bears and is glad*

^aPs 48:11; Zeph 3:14

Psalm 97:9

¹Or *supernatural powers*

^aPs 83:18

^bEx 18:11; Ps 95:3; 96:4; 135:5

Psalm 97:10

^aPs 34:14; Prov 8:13; Amos 5:15; Rom 12:9

^bPs 31:23; 145:20; Prov 2:8

^cPs 37:40; Jer 15:21; Dan 3:28

Psalm 97:11

^aJob 22:28; Ps 112:4; Prov 4:18

^bPs 64:10

Psalm 97:12

¹Lit *for the memory of His holiness*

^aPs 32:11

^bPs 30:4

Targum

Psa. 97:1 The LORD reigns, let the earth rejoice, let the many isles be glad. ² Clouds of glory and darkness are around him; righteousness and justice are the place where his throne is set. ³ Fire will go before him, and it burns around his oppressors. ⁴ His lightnings illuminate the world; the earth saw and trembled. ⁵ The mountains will melt like wax in the presence of the LORD, in the presence of the master of all the earth. ⁶ The angels of the height will tell of his righteousness, and all the peoples will see his glory. ⁷ All who worship idols will be ashamed, who pride themselves on a false god; and all the peoples who worship a false god will bow down in his presence. ⁸ The assembly of Zion has heard and rejoiced, and the daughters of the house of Judah exult, because of your judgments, O LORD. ⁹ For you are the LORD, the supreme one over all the inhabitants of the earth; you are greatly exalted over all that is revered. ¹⁰ O you who love the LORD, hate evil, because the Almighty protects the souls of his pious ones; from the hands of the wicked he will deliver them. ¹¹ Light has shone and is hidden for the righteous, and joy for the upright of heart. ¹² Be glad, O righteous, in the word of the LORD, and give thanks at the mention of his holy name.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was written by Moses and dedicated to the tribe of Joseph (Ephraim and Manassah). Joshua was from the tribe of Joseph and led Israel into the Promised Land and conquered it. The Psalm alludes to the future times of peace.

Verse four

It was a dark era for Israel while they traveled in the wilderness for forty years. The LORD promised to bring the dark era to an end like a thunderstorm. When Joshua took an army to Jericho and walked around the city seven times, the sound of the walls crashing down had to be tremendous. The LORD's people were victorious as they entered the and promised to them through Abraham.

But once His bolts of lightning have lit up the world of man, when the earth has gained insight and gone into labor.

Verses eight and nine

One day the LORD will be worshiped throughout the earth. When this happens, joy will return to Zion, the ancient eternal Sanctuary of the LORD (Jerusalem was where both Temples were built for the LORD. All of Judah will rejoice that day.

But Zion has heard it and is glad, then the daughters of Judah will rejoice because of Your judgments, O LORD;

That you, LORD, are now most high over all the earth, exalted far above all gods. =

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

